

VIBRATION BEHAVIORS OF 1D LATTICE TRUSS STRUCTURES UNDER DIFFERENT CONSTRAINS

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ABSTRACT

To reveal beam-vibration modes of one-dimensional (1D) lattice truss composite structures (LTCSs) under different constrains, finite element modeling (FEM) method and theoretical models were developed. When the column is long and inclinations is small, it will occurs the beam-like vibration modes. For beam-like vibration, the 1st order vibration frequency depends on the column length and is the inclination has slight influence. The constraint has a great influence on the 1st order vibration frequency. Continuum beam-like model under different constrains was suggested to predict the 1st order frequency of the LTSC. The predictions are consistent with the numerical simulations and these models can be applied in engineering to instruct the dynamic design of the LTSC.

1 INTRODUCTION

Lattice truss composite structures (LTCSs), including space-truss structure [1-4], planar grid structure [5], hierarchical lattice structure [6], woven lattice sandwich structure and tube-like lattice column [7, 8], are known for their high specific stiffness and strength [1-8]. Among them, IsoTruss[®] [9-12] is a 1D LTCS and usually applied as columns or beams to sustain axial compression and bending in aerospace engineering. Length of this tube-like structure is much greater than its diameter. Lai et al. [13] developed a flexible tooling method. In their compression experiments, the LTCS failed at fracture of the strut. More failure modes have been observed by Rackliffe et al. [9, 14] in their experiments, including global and local buckling. Sui et al. [15] divided the local buckling into shell-like buckling and mono-cell buckling, depending on the buckling wave length. This weight efficient structure has the potential to enhance innumerable applications in aerospace structures.

Several methods have been discussed in the literature, and they are reviewed in the survey paper [16]. Among them, the substitute continuum approach has several advantages, and has proved to be suitable for the analysis of large repetitive lattices [16]. The one includes methods in which the continuum behaviour is assumed a priori (e.g. a Timoshenko-beam for a beam-like lattice). Then, the problem amounts to finding the equivalent continuum properties. The equivalence can be defined on the energies [16-20], or on the constitutive relations, by transforming the force-displacement relationships in the repetitive lattice into constitutive equations in the continuum model [21].

In this paper, beam vibration behaviors under different constraints of 8-node LTCS columns were discussed through finite element (FE) modeling method. Equivalent model was proposed to predict the 1st order frequency of LTCS structures.

2 MODELING

FEM based on ANSYS was proposed to discuss the vibration behavior of the 8-node LTCS columns under different constraints. To reveal the first vibration mode of the 8-node LTCS columns with different column length (L) and helical inclination (φ), an APDL (ANSYS Parametric

Design Language) program was written to fulfill the FEM simulation automatically. The model of the 8-node LTCS columns is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Front view and top view of the 8-node LTCS columns

In simulation, the Young's modulus of the members (E_s) is 50 GPa, the density of the members (ρ) is 1.33 g/cm³ and the radius of the members (r) is 1.5 mm. The radius of the column (R) is 50 mm.

3 BEAM-LIKE DYNAMIC RESPOSE

3.1 Built-in-free constrains

The 1st mode of FEM results under built-in-free constraints are listed in in Figs. 2, where the column length varies from 500 mm to 1500 mm and the inclination of helical members varies from 30⁰ to 60⁰. When the column is long enough or the helical inclination is small enough, the LTCS just vibrates as a continuum beam. For example, the 1500 mm long column has typical beam-like vibrational behaviors. The 1st mode beam-like vibration has a quarter wave-length. The 1000 mm long column has typical beam-like vibrational behaviors just as the 1500 mm long column. When the inclination increases to 60⁰, all of the first are beam-like. For the 500 mm long column, the beam-like mode also appears as the 1st mode.

Length	$\varphi = 30^0$	$\varphi = 40^0$	$\varphi = 50^0$	$\varphi = 60^0$
500mm				

Fig. 2 Bulit-in-free vibration modes of the 8-node LTCS columns

3.2 Clamped-clamped constraints

The 1st mode of FEM results under clamped-clamped constraints are listed in in Figs. 3, where the column length varies from 500 mm to 1500 mm and the inclination of helical members varies from 30⁰ to 60⁰. When the column is long enough or the helical inclination is small enough, the LTCS just vibrates as a continuum beam. For example, the 1500 mm long column has typical beam-like vibrational behaviors. The 1st mode beam-like vibration has a quarter wave-length. The 1000 mm long column has typical beam-like vibrational behaviors just as the 1500 mm long column. For the 500 mm long column, the beam-like mode appears as the 1st mode when $\varphi = 30^0$ and $\varphi = 40^0$.

Fig. 3 Clamped-clamped vibration modes of the 8-node LTCS columns

3.3 Simply-supported constraints

The 1st mode of FEM results under clamped-clamped constraints are listed in in Figs. 4, where the column length varies from 500 mm to 1500 mm and the inclination of helical members varies from 30⁰ to 60⁰. When the column is long enough or the helical inclination is small enough, the LTCS just vibrates as a continuum beam. For example, the 1500 mm long column has typical beam-like vibrational behaviors. The 1st mode beam-like vibration has a quarter wave-length. The 1000 mm long column has typical beam-like vibrational behaviors just as the 1500 mm long column. When the inclination increases to 60⁰, all of the first are beam-like. For the 500 mm long column, the beam-like mode also appears as the 1st mode.

Fig. 4 Simply-supported vibration modes of the 8-node LTCS columns.

3.4 1st order frequency

As the vibration response of the 8-node LTCS columns changes with the column length and the helical member inclination, the 1st order frequency has special changing rules, as shown in Fig. 5. Under different constraints, the 1000 mm and 1500 mm long columns vibrate as a beam. The 1st mode frequency keeps quasi-unchanged. The 500 mm vibrate as a beam when the inclination is small. So initially the 1st mode frequency keeps quasi-unchanged and then decreases quasi-linearly. When the LTCS vibrates as a beam, its 1st frequency is reduced when the column is longer but is almost irrelevant to the inclination of the helical members. The constraints has great influence on the 1st frequency.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 5 The 1st order frequency of the 8-node LTCS columns under different constraints: (a) bulit-in-free vibration;(b) clamped-clamped vibration;(c) simply-supported vibration.

4 THEORIES

According to the numerical simulation, when the column is long enough or the helical inclination is small enough, the the 8-node LTCS columns. just behaves as a continuum beam. The first order frequency under bulit-in-free constraints, ω_1 , is given by [22]

$$\omega_1 = \left[\frac{1.875}{H} \right]^2 \sqrt{\frac{EI}{\rho S}} = 3.516 H^{-\frac{3}{2}} \sqrt{\frac{E(8-4\sqrt{2})\pi r^2 R^2}{\frac{2n\pi H \rho r^2}{\sin \varphi} + n\pi H \rho r^2}} \quad (1)$$

The 1st order frequency, f_1 , is given by

$$f_1 = \frac{\omega_1}{2\pi} = \frac{0.93 \times 10^8}{H^2} \sqrt{\frac{\sin(\varphi)}{2 + \sin(\varphi)}} \quad (2)$$

Eq. (2) consistently predicts the 1st order frequency of the 8-node LTCS columns with varying helical inclination, as shown in Fig. 6(a).

The first order frequency under clamped-clamped constraints, ω_2 , is given by [22]

$$\omega_2 = \left[\frac{3\pi}{H} \right]^2 \sqrt{\frac{EI}{\rho S}} = 22.184 H^{-\frac{3}{2}} \sqrt{\frac{E(8-4\sqrt{2})\pi r^2 R^2}{2n\pi H \rho r^2 + n\pi H \rho r^2 \sin \varphi}} \quad (3)$$

The 1st order frequency, f_2 , is given by

$$f_2 = \frac{\omega_2}{2\pi} = \frac{5.85 \times 10^8}{H^2} \sqrt{\frac{\sin(\varphi)}{2 + \sin(\varphi)}} \quad (4)$$

Eq. (4) consistently predicts the 1st order frequency of the 8-node LTCS columns with varying helical inclination, as shown in Fig. 6(b).

The first order frequency under simply-supported constraints, ω_3 , is given by [22]

$$\omega_3 = \left[\frac{\pi}{H} \right]^2 \sqrt{\frac{EI}{\rho S}} = 9.859 H^{-\frac{3}{2}} \sqrt{\frac{E(8-4\sqrt{2})\pi r^2 R^2}{2n\pi H \rho r^2 + n\pi H \rho r^2 \sin \varphi}} \quad (5)$$

The first order frequency, f_3 , is given by

$$f_3 = \frac{\omega_4}{2\pi} = \frac{2.25 \times 10^8}{H^2} \sqrt{\frac{\sin(\varphi)}{2 + \sin(\varphi)}} \quad (6)$$

Eq. (6) consistently predicts the 1st order frequency of the 8-node LTCS columns. with varying helical inclination, as shown in Fig. 6(c).

It is found that The first order frequency under different constraints is dependent on the column length and the helical inclination. Constraints have the great influence on the first order frequency. The first order frequency under clamped-clamped constraint is higher than others. The first order frequency under built-in-free constraint is the lowest.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 6 The 1st frequency and the prediction of the 8-node LTCS columns: (a)bulit-in-free vibration;(b) clamped-clamped vibration;(c) simply-supported vibration.

5 CONCLUSION

According to the research, based on simulation analysis with ANSYS ,when the 8-node LTCS columns. is long enough under different constraints ,it has the typical vibration modes: beam like-modes.

Long columns and small inclinations easily induce beam-like vibration modes and the 1st order vibration frequency depends on the column length and is the inclination has slight influence. Longitudinal truss member stiffness has key influence to the 1st order vibration frequency.

Continuum beam-like model under different constraints was developed to predict the 1st order frequency of the 8-node LTCS columns. The predictions are consistent with the numerical simulations and these models can be applied in engineering to instruct the dynamic design of the 8-node LTCS columns

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